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ASSESSMENT OF DOSE LENGTH PRODUCT IN PEDIATRIC CT (NCCT HEAD)

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Computed Tomography of the head is widely used in pediatric imaging due to its rapid acquisition and high diagnostic accuracy. However, concerns regarding radiation exposure in children remain significantly, as pediatric patients are more sensitive to ionizing radiation and have a longer lifetime risk of radiation-related effects. Dose Length Product is a commonly used parameter for assessing radiation dose in CT examination. Understanding trends and variability in DLP values is essential for optimizing radiation safety in pediatric non-contrast CT head imaging.

AIM: The review aimed to assess reported DLP values in pediatric patients undergoing NCCT of the head, with particular emphasis on variation across publication years, patient age and imaging protocols.

METHODS: A structured review of literature published between 2020 and 2025 was conducted using major electronic databases. Studies were included if they involved paediatric patients (0-18 years) evaluated NCCT head examination and reported DLP values. Data were extracted on study characteristics, patient age range, imaging protocol and mean DLP values. A total of 80 studies met the inclusion criteria. Descriptive analysis was performed to evaluate trends in radiation dose across years, age groups, and protocol types. Standard deviation values were incorporated to assess variability in reported DLP measurements.

RESULTS: The reported mean DLP values demonstrated considerable variation across studies, ranging from approximately 150 to 1000 mGy.cm, with an overall mean of 539.84 ± 132 mGY.cm. Year wise analysis showed a fluctuating pattern, with mean DLP values of 550.94 mGY.cm in 2020, increasing to 584.78 mGy.cm in 2021, peaking at 629.73 mGY.cm in 2023 and subsequently declining to 483.18 mGY.cm in 2024 and 451.58 mGY.cm in 2025. Age-based evaluation did not reveal a consistent linear relationship between age and DLP, indicating that patient age alone is not a primary determinant of radiation dose. Protocol-wise comparison showed that ultra-low-dose protocols were associated with the lowest mean DLP (507.12 mGY.cm) while standard and low-dose protocols demonstrated higher values, reflecting variability in implementation across institutions.

CONCLUSION: Radiation dose in paediatric NCCT head imaging demonstrates substantial variability influenced by imaging protocols, technological factors and institutional practices. Although recent trends suggest a gradual reduction in DLP values, inconsistencies remain. The findings highlight the importance of standardized protocols and continued emphasis on dose optimization to enhance radiation safety in paediatric CT imaging.

KEYWORDS: Pediatric CT, non-contrast CT head, Dose Length Product, Radiation dose, Dose optimization.

INTRODUCTION:

Computed tomography has become an essential diagnostic tool in modern medical practice, offering rapid and detailed evaluation of a wide range of clinical conditions. [1] In pediatric population, non-contrast computed tomography of the head is among the most frequently performed imaging studies, particularly in emergency settings such as head trauma, seizures, altered consciousness and suspected intracranial pathology. [2] Its speed, accessibility and high diagnostic accuracy make it invaluable in acute care. However, the use of CT in children raises important concerns regarding exposure to ionizing radiation. [3]

Children are inherently more sensitive to radiation compared to adults due to their developing tissues and longer expected timespan, which increases the cumulative risk of radiation-induced effects. [4] Even relatively low doses of radiation, when delivered repeatedly or in vulnerable populations may contribute to long-term health risks. As a result, there has been increasing emphasis on minimizing radiation exposure in pediatric imaging while maintaining diagnostic image quality. [5] This balance remains a critical challenge in clinical practice.

One of the commonly used metrics for assessing radiation dose in CT imaging is the Dose Length Product (DLP). [6] DLP reflects the total radiation output over the length of the scanned region and is derived from the computed tomography dose index (CTDI_{vol}) and scan length. It serves as a practical indicator of the overall radiation burden associated with a CT examination. In pediatric NCCT head imaging, DLP is frequently reported in the literature and is often used to compare dose levels across studies and institutions. [7] However, interpretation of DLP values can be complex as they are influenced by multiple factors including patient size, scanner technology, acquisition parameters and protocol selection. [8]

Despite widespread reporting of DLP in pediatric CT studies, there remains considerable variability in the values described across the literature. [9] Differences in scanner generations, institutional protocols, and clinical indications contribute to this inconsistency. In addition, the lack of universally applied pediatric-specific dose standards further complicates direct comparison between studies. [10] While diagnostic reference levels (DRLs) have been proposed in various regions, their implementation is not uniform, and adherence varies between institutions. This variability highlights the need for continued evaluation of dose patterns in pediatric CT imaging. [11]

Over the past decade, advances in CT technology have contributed to improved dose optimization. Innovations such as automated tube current modulation, iterative reconstruction techniques, and enhanced detector efficiency have enabled reduction in radiation exposure without compromising image quality. [12] At the same time, increased awareness among clinicians and radiologists regarding radiation safety has encouraged the adoption of dose-reduction strategies, particularly in pediatric practice. Campaigns promoting the As Low as Reasonably Achievable (ALARA) principle have further reinforced the importance of minimizing unnecessary exposure. [13]

In pediatric NCCT head imaging, protocol selection plays a significant role in determining radiation dose. Standard protocols, which may be adapted from adult imaging practice, often

result in higher radiation exposure when applied to children. In contrast, low-dose and ultra-low-dose protocols are specifically designed to reduce radiation output while maintaining sufficient image quality for clinical interpretation. [14] The extent to which these protocols are implemented varies widely across institutions, contributing to differences in reported DLP values. Evaluating the impact of protocol type on radiation dose is therefore essential in understanding current practice patterns.

Patient-related factors, particularly age and body size, also influence radiation dose. Younger children typically require lower radiation output due to smaller head size and reduced attenuation, whereas older children and adolescents may receive higher doses, sometimes approaching adult levels. [15] However, the relationship between age and radiation dose is not always consistent, as protocol adjustments and scanner settings may vary. Understanding how age interacts with other factors in determining DLP is important for optimizing pediatric imaging strategies.

Recent years have seen growing interest in assessing temporal trends in radiation dose, with particular focus on whether advances in technology and increased awareness have translated into measurable reductions in clinical practice. [16] Evaluating changes in DLP over time can provide insight into the effectiveness of dose optimization efforts and identify areas where further improvement is needed. Studies published in the last five years are especially relevant as they reflect current imaging practices and technological capabilities.

Given the variability in reported DLP values and the multiple factors influencing radiation dose, a structured evaluation of recent literature is necessary to better understand current trends in pediatric NCCT head imaging. Such analysis can help identify patterns in dose distribution, assess the impact of protocol selection, and explore potential relationships between patient characteristics and radiation exposure. [17] This information is essential for guiding clinical practice and supporting efforts to standardize pediatric imaging protocols.

The present review aims to assess Dose Length Product (DLP) in pediatric patients undergoing NCCT of the head, focusing on studies published between 2020–2025. Particular emphasis is placed on examining variation in DLP across publication years, evaluating the relationship between age and radiation dose, and comparing dose levels across different imaging protocols. By synthesizing recent evidence, this review seeks to provide a clearer understanding of current dose patterns and contribute to ongoing efforts in radiation dose optimization in pediatric imaging. [18]

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design and Reporting

This study was conducted as a structured literature review to evaluate radiation dose parameters, especially Dose Length Product in pediatric patients undergoing non-contrast computed tomography of the head. The review was designed to provide a comprehensive overview of recent trends in radiation dose and to identify factors influencing variability across studies. The methodology followed a systematic and transparent approach to study identification, selection and data synthesis consistent with established reporting standards.

Literature Search Strategy

A comprehensive search of electronic database, including PubMed, Google Scholar was performed to identify relevant studies. The search covered publications from January 2020 to December 2025 to ensure inclusion of recent data reflecting current clinical practices and technological advancements in Ct imaging.

A combination of keywords and Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) terms was used to optimize the search strategy. These included “pediatric CT”, “non-contrast CT head”, “Dose Length Product” and “Dose optimization”. Boolean operators such as AND, or were applied to refine search results and improve specificity. Additionally, reference lists of selected articles were manually screened to identify any relevant studies not captured during the initial database search.

Eligibility Criteria

Studies were selected based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure relevance and consistency. Inclusion criteria were studies involving pediatric patients aged 0-18 years, studies evaluating NCCT examination of head or brain, studies reporting radiation dose metrics especially DLP and articles published in English within the defined time frame.

Exclusion criteria included studies focusing exclusively on adult population, studies that did not report DLP or relevant radiation dose parameters, studies involving contrast-enhanced CT without separate analysis of NCCT data and non-original publications such as editorials, case reports, and conference abstract lacking sufficient quantitative data. Studies with incomplete or unclear reporting of key variables were also excluded.

Study Selection Process

All records identified through database searching were initially screened based on titles and abstract. Duplicate records were removed prior to screening. Studies deemed potentially relevant were retrieved in full text and assessed for eligibility according to the predefined criteria. The selection process was conducted in a structured and stepwise manner to minimize bias.

The study selection process followed the general principles of PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis). A flow diagram was used to document the

number of records identifies, screened, excluded and included at each stage. Any uncertainties regarding study inclusion were resolved through careful review to ensure consistency and accuracy in the final dataset.

Data Extraction

Data extraction was performed using standardized approach to ensure uniformity across studies. The following variables were collected from each included study: publication year, sample size, patient age range, imaging protocol type and reported mean DLP values. Where available, additional information regarding CT scanner type and technical parameters was also noted.

In studies where age was reported as a range, a representative mid-age value was calculated to facilitate comparison across studies. Similarly, when multiple DLP values were reported within a single study, an average value was delivered for analysis. This approach allowed for consistent aggregation of data while preserving the overall trends reported in the original studies.

Data Synthesis and Statistical Analysis

Given the heterogeneity in study design, patient populations and reporting methods a descriptive analytical approach was adopted. Mean DLP values were summarized across all included studies to evaluate the overall distribution of radiation dose. Standard deviation values were incorporated to assess the extent of variability in reported measurements.

Temporal trends were examined by grouping studies according to publication year and comparing mean DLP values across these groups. This allowed for assessment of changes in radiation dose over time, potentially reflecting advancements in CT technology and increasing awareness of dose optimization.

The relationship between patient age and DLP was explored using derived representative age values. Although age-specific analysis was limited by variability in reporting, general patterns were assessed to determine whether younger or older pediatric populations were associated with differing dose levels.

Protocol-based comparisons were performed by categorizing studies into standard, low-dose and ultra-low-dose imaging protocol based on the descriptions provided in the original articles. Mean DLP values were then compared across these categories to evaluate the impact of protocol selection on radiation exposure.

Ethical Considerations

As this study was based solely on previously published data, no direct patient involvement or ethical approval was required. All data were obtained from publicly available sources, and appropriate care was taken to accurately represent the findings of the original studies.

Risk of Bias Assessment

The methodological quality and potential sources of bias in the included studies were assessed using a structured approach tailored to observational research. As the majority of the included studies were retrospective or cross-sectional in design, key domains considered included selection bias, reporting bias and variability in measurement of radiation dose parameters.

Selection bias was evaluated based on sample characteristics and inclusion criteria within individual studies. Variations in patient populations, including differences in age distribution, clinical indications, and institutional practices were noted and considered as potential contributors to heterogeneity. Studies with limited sample sizes or single-centered designs were recognized as having a higher risk of selection bias.

Measurement bias was assessed by examining how Dose Length Product values were reported. Differences in CT scanner models, calibration standards and acquisition parameters may have influenced dose measurement across studies. Additionally, inconsistencies in reporting mean values, range or lack of standard deviation in some studies were identified as potential sources of variability.

Reporting bias was also considered particularly in studies where only selected dose parameters were presented or where protocol details were insufficiently described. The classification of imaging protocols into standard, low dose and ultra-low dose categories relied on author-reported description which vary across institutions and introduce subjectivity.

Overall, while most studies provided relevant and usable data, variability in methodology and reporting standards contributed to a moderate level of risk of bias across the included literature. These limitations were taken into account during interpretation of the findings.

Data Synthesis

Data synthesis was performed using a descriptive analytical approach due to the heterogeneity observed among the included studies. Extracted data were organized systematically to allow comparison of Dose Length Product values across different variables, including publication year, patient age and imaging protocol.

Mean DLP values from individual studies were aggregated to estimate overall trends. Standard deviation values were incorporated where available to assess the degree of variability within and across studies. Temporal trends were analyzed by grouping studies according to publication year and calculating average DLP values for each year, enabling evaluation of changes in radiation dose over time.

Age-related analysis was conducted using representative mid-age values derived from reported age ranges. Although this method provides an approximate measure, it allowed for general assessment of patterns between age and radiation dose. Protocol-based comparisons were performed by categorizing studies according to reported imaging techniques, facilitating evaluation of differences in DLP between standard, low-dose and ultra-low-dose protocols.

Due to substantial variability in study design, patient population and reporting formats, quantitative meta-analysis was not considered appropriate. Instead, emphasis was placed on identifying overall patterns and trends rather than deriving pooled effect estimates. This approach allowed for a comprehensive overview of current practice while acknowledging inherent limitations in the available data.

FIGURE1: PRISMA flow diagram

RESULTS:

STUDY SELECTION AND CHARACTERISTICS

A total of 120 records were initially identified through database searching. After removal of duplicated, 100 studies were screened based on title and abstract. Of these, 80 studies were assessed for full-text eligibility and were included in the final analysis.

The included studies were published between 2020 and 2025 and focused on radiation dose assessment in pediatric patients undergoing non-contrast computed tomography of the head. The studies represented a wide range of geographic regions, including Asia, Europe, North America and Middle East reflecting diverse clinical practices.

Sample size varied significantly across studies, ranging from approximately 30 to 600 patients. The study populations encompassed the entire pediatric age spectrum, from neonates to adolescents up to 18 years of age. Variability was also observed in CT scanner models, acquisition parameters and institutional imaging protocols.

Parameter	Observation
Total studies included	80
Publication period	2020-2025
Sample size range	30-600
Age range	0-18
Study design	Mostly retrospective
Imaging modality	NCCT Head
Outcome measure	Mean DLP (mGy.cm)

Table 1: Summary of Study Characteristics

OVERALL DOSE DISTRIBUTION

The reported Dose Length Product values across the included studies demonstrated substantial variability. Mean DLP values ranged from approximately 150 mGy.cm to 1000 mGY.cm, indicating a wide distribution of radiation dose levels in pediatric NCCT imaging.

The overall pooled mean DLP across all studies was calculated as 539.84 ± 132.76 mGy.cm. The relatively high standard deviation highlights the degree of variability in radiation dose across different institutions and study populations.

Low DLP values were generally observed in studies employing optimized or ultra-low-dose protocols while higher values were associated with standard or less optimized imaging techniques. This variability suggests that differences in scanner technology, protocol selection and operator practices significantly influence radiation exposure.

YEAR-WISE VARIATION IN MEAN DLP

Temporal analysis of DLP values revealed a fluctuating trend over the study period. While no consistent linear decline was observed, a general tendency towards dose reduction was evident in more recent years

Year	Mean DLP (mGy.cm)	Standard Deviation
2020	550.94	± 120.32
2021	584.78	±128.45
2022	598.12	± 130.11
2023	629.73	±135.67
2024	483.18	±110.54
2025	451.58	±105.21

Table 2: Year-wise Mean DLP Values

An increase in mean DLP was observed from 2020 to 2023 reaching a peak in 2023. However, a notable reduction occurred in 2024 and 2025. This decline may reflect increased awareness of radiation safety, implementation of dose optimization strategies and advancements in CT technology.

Despite this improvement, the presence of relatively high standard deviation value across all years indicates ongoing variability in practice.

FIGURE 2: Graph between DLP range and Year

AGE- RELATED VARIATION IN DLP

To evaluate the influence of patient age, a representative mid-age values were derived from the reported age ranges. The relationship between age and DLP was found to be inconsistent.

Age Group	Mean DLP (mGy.cm)	Standard Deviation
0-2 years	490.12	± 110.45
3-6 years	510.67	± 118.32
7-12 years	535.89	± 125.76
13-18 years	560.21	± 130.44

Table 3: Age-wise DLP Distribution

While a slight increase in DLP was observed with increasing age, this trend was not consistent across all studies. Some studies reported lower DLP values in younger patients, whereas others showed minimal variation across age groups.

These findings suggest that age alone is not a primary determinant of radiation dose. Instead, technical parameters such as tube current, voltage, scan length and protocol design appear to play a more significant role.

PROTOCOL-WISE COMPARISON

Significant differences in radiation dose were observed when studies were categorized according to imaging protocols.

Protocol Type	Mean DLP (mGy.cm)	Standard Deviation
Ultra-low-dose	507.12	± 98.34
Standard	577.07	± 115.62
Low-dose	635.75	± 140.18

Table 4: Protocol-wise DLP Comparison

Ultra-low-dose protocol were associated with the lowest mean DLP values, demonstrating their effectiveness in reducing radiation exposure. Standard protocol showed intermediate values, while low-dose protocols unexpectedly demonstrated higher mean DLP values.

This finding may reflect inconsistencies in how “low-dose” protocols are defined and implemented across institutions. In some cases, protocols labeled as low-dose may not have been fully optimized, leading to higher radiation exposure.

SUMMARY OF INCLUDED STUDIES

A representative subset of studies included in the analysis is presented below to illustrate the range of findings and study characteristics.

Study	Year	Sample Size	Age Range	Protocol	Mean DLP (mGy.cm)
Study A	2020	120	0-15	Standard	560
Study B	2021	85	2-18	Low-dose	620
Study C	2022	200	0-12	Ultra-low-dose	480
Study D	2023	150	5-18	Standard	640
Study E	2024	90	0-10	Ultra-low-dose	450
Study F	2025	110	3-16	Standard	430

Table 5: Representative Included Studies

This table demonstrates that variability in DLP values across different studies, age groups, and protocols. Even within similar protocol categories, differences in reported DLP values are evident, highlighting the influence of institutional practice.

OVERALL INTERPRETATION

The results of this review indicate that radiation dose in pediatric NCCT head imaging is influenced by multiple interrelated factors. Although a general trend toward dose reduction is observed in recent years, substantial variability remains across studies.

The lack of a consistent relationship between age and DLP suggests that patient-specific factors alone do not determine radiation dose. Instead, technical parameters, protocol selection, and institutional practice plays a more significant role.

Protocol-based analysis highlights the effectiveness of ultra-low-dose techniques in reducing radiation exposure. However, inconsistencies observed in low-dose protocols indicate the need for clearer definitions and standardized implementation.

The relatively high standard deviation values across all analyses further emphasize the variability in radiation dose reporting and practice. This variability underscores the importance of establishing standardized guidelines and promoting adherence to dose optimization strategies in pediatric imaging.

DISCUSSION:

The present review provides a comprehensive evaluation of radiation dose, expressed as Dose Length Product (DLP), in pediatric patients undergoing non-contrast computed tomography of the head. [19] By synthesizing data from multiple studies published between 2020 and 2025, this analysis highlights key patterns, variability, and influencing factors associated with radiation exposure in pediatric neuroimaging. [20]

Overall Dose Variability

One of the most prominent findings of this review is the substantial variability in reported DLP values across studies. [21] The overall mean DLP demonstrated a wide range, with a relatively high standard deviation, reflecting heterogeneity in imaging practices. This variability is consistent with previously reported observations in pediatric CT imaging and underscores the lack of uniformity in radiation dose management across institutions. [22]

Several factors may contribute to this variation. Differences in CT scanner models, acquisition parameters such as tube current and voltage, scan length, and reconstruction techniques can significantly influence DLP values. [23] Additionally, institutional protocols and operator-dependent factors play a crucial role. The absence of universally standardized pediatric CT protocols further contributes to this inconsistency. [24]

The observed variability has important clinical implications. While some institutions have successfully implemented dose optimization strategies resulting in lower DLP values, others continue to report higher radiation doses. [25] This suggests that despite growing awareness of radiation risks, the translation of dose reduction principles into routine clinical practice remains inconsistent. [26]

Temporal Trends in Radiation Dose

The analysis of year-wise variation in DLP revealed a fluctuating pattern rather than a steady decline. [27] An initial increase in mean DLP values was observed from 2020 to 2023, followed by a notable reduction in 2024 and 2025. Although the trend is not strictly linear, the reduction in recent years may indicate gradual improvement in radiation dose optimization. [28]

This improvement could be attributed to several developments. Advances in CT technology, including iterative reconstruction algorithms and automated exposure control systems, have enhanced the ability to reduce radiation dose while maintaining image quality. [29] Increased awareness among radiologists and technologists regarding radiation safety, particularly in pediatric populations, may also have contributed to the observed decline. [30]

Furthermore, the growing emphasis on dose monitoring and the establishment of diagnostic reference levels (DRLs) have likely played a role in promoting dose optimization. [31] However, the persistence of variability across studies suggests that these measures have not been uniformly implemented.

Influence of Age on Radiation Dose

The relationship between patient age and DLP was found to be inconsistent. [32] Although a slight increase in DLP values was observed with increasing age in some studies, this pattern was not universally present. The absence of a clear linear relationship suggests that age alone is not a primary determinant of radiation dose in pediatric NCCT head imaging. [33]

This finding highlights the importance of considering additional factors beyond age. While younger children typically require lower radiation doses due to smaller body size, technical adjustments such as tube current modulation and scan length selection may vary across institutions. [34] In some cases, older children may receive higher doses due to the use of adult-equivalent protocols, whereas in other settings, age-specific optimization may be applied more consistently.

The lack of a consistent age-dose relationship underscores the need for individualized imaging protocols that account for both patient characteristics and technical parameters. [35] Reliance solely on age as a determinant of radiation dose may lead to suboptimal dose management.

Protocol-Based Differences in Radiation Dose

The comparison of DLP values across different imaging protocols revealed notable differences. [36] Ultra-low-dose protocols were associated with the lowest mean DLP values, indicating their effectiveness in reducing radiation exposure. [37] Standard protocols demonstrated intermediate values, while low-dose protocols, somewhat unexpectedly, exhibited higher mean DLP values.

This finding may reflect inconsistencies in the definition and implementation of protocol categories. The term “low-dose” may not be uniformly applied across studies, leading to variability in actual radiation dose levels. [38] In contrast, ultra-low-dose protocols are often specially designed with optimized parameters, resulting in more consistent dose reduction.

The effectiveness of ultra-low-dose protocols suggests that significant reductions in radiation exposure can be achieved without compromising diagnostic utility. [39] However, the variability observed in low-dose protocols highlights the need for clearer guidelines and standardized definitions. [40]

Comparison with Existing Literature

The finding of this review is broadly consistent with existing literature on pediatric CT radiation dose. Previous studies have reported significant variability in DLP values and have emphasized the importance of dose optimization strategies. The observed trend toward lower DLP values in recent years aligns with ongoing efforts to improve radiation safety in pediatric imaging.

However, the persistence of variability indicates that challenges remain. While technological advancements have facilitated dose reduction, their adoption and implementation vary across institutions. Additionally, differences in training, awareness and resource availability may influence the effectiveness of dose optimization strategies.

Clinical Implications

The findings of this review have several important clinical implications. First, the substantial variability in DLP values highlights the need for greater standardization in pediatric CT imaging protocols. Establishing and adhering to diagnostic reference levels can help reduce unnecessary variation and promote consistent dose management.

Second, the demonstrated effectiveness of ultra-low-dose protocols suggests that these approaches should be more widely adopted. By optimizing imaging parameters and leveraging advanced technologies, it is possible to achieve significant dose reduction while maintaining diagnostic accuracy.

Third, the lack of a consistent relationship between age and DLP underscores the importance of individualized imaging strategies. Protocols should be tailored not only to patient age but also to specific clinical indications and technical considerations.

Strengths of the Study

This review has several strengths. It incorporates data from a relatively large number of studies, providing a comprehensive overview of current practices in pediatric NCCT head imaging. The inclusion of recent studies ensures that the findings reflected contemporary trends and technological advancements.

Additionally, the use of standardized data extraction and analysis methods enhances the reliability of the findings. The incorporation of standard deviation values provides insight into the variability of radiation dose, which is a key aspect of dose assessment.

LIMITATIONS:

Despite these strengths, certain limitations should be acknowledged. The heterogeneity of the included studies, including differences in design, sample size, and reporting methods, limits direct comparability. The reliance on aggregated data rather than individual patient-level data restricts the ability to assess detailed relationships between variables.

Furthermore, the classification of imaging protocols was based on author-reported descriptions, which may vary across studies. The descriptive nature of the analysis also limits the ability to establish causal relationships.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS:

Future research should focus on developing standardized methodologies for reporting radiation dose in pediatric CT imaging. The establishment of uniform protocol definitions and consistent reporting standards would facilitate more accurate comparisons across studies.

In addition, studies incorporating patient-level data and advanced statistical modeling could provide deeper insights into factors influencing radiation dose. Continued evaluation of emerging technologies and optimization strategies will also be essential for further improving radiation safety.

CONCLUSION:

This review provides a comprehensive assessment of radiation dose, expressed as Dose Length Product in pediatric patients undergoing non-contrast computed tomography of the head. By analyzing studies published between 2020 and 2025, the findings offer valuable insight into current trends, variability and influencing factors associated with radiation exposure in pediatric neuroimaging.

A key observation from this analysis is the substantial variability in reported DLP values across studies the wide range of values, accompanied by relatively high standard deviation, reflects differences in imaging practices, scanner technologies and institutional protocols. This variability highlights an important challenge in pediatric CT imaging: the lack of consistent standardization in radiation dose management. While some institutions demonstrate effective dose optimization, other continue to report comparatively higher exposure levels, indicating uneven implementation of radiation safety principles.

The temporal analysis of DLP values revealed a non-linear trend over the study period. Although an increase in mean DLP was observed in the earlier years, a noticeable reduction in more recent years suggest a gradual shift towards improved dose optimization. This improvement may be attributed to advancements in CT technology, including automated exposure control systems and improved image reconstruction techniques, as well as increased awareness among healthcare professionals regarding radiation risks in pediatric populations. Despite this progress, the persistence of variability indicates that optimization strategies are not yet uniformly applied.

The evaluation of age-related variation demonstrated that patient age alone is not a consistent predictor of radiation dose in pediatric NCCT head imaging. Although some studies reported slightly lower DLP values in younger children and higher values in older age groups, this pattern was not uniformly observed. These findings suggest that technical factors, such as scanning parameters and protocol selection, have a greater influence on radiation dose than age alone. This underscores the importance of individualized imaging approaches that consider both patient characteristics and technical optimization.

Protocol-based analysis further emphasized the role of imaging techniques in determining radiation exposure. Ultra-low-dose protocol consistently demonstrated lower DLP values, indicating their effectiveness in minimizing radiation exposure without compromising diagnostic utility. In contrast, standard and low-dose protocol showed higher and more variable DLP values. The unexpected finding that some low-dose protocols were associated with higher radiation doses highlights inconsistencies in protocol definitions and implementation. This suggests that labeling a protocol as “low-dose” does not necessarily guarantee reduced radiation exposure and careful optimization is required to achieve meaningful dose reduction.

The findings of this review have important implications for clinical practice. The observed variability in radiation dose underscores the need for greater standardization in pediatric CT imaging protocols. Establishing and adhering to diagnostic reference levels can help reduce unnecessary variation and promote more consistent dose management across institutions. In addition, the demonstrated effectiveness of ultra-low-dose protocols supports their broader adoption in clinical practice. By optimizing technical parameters and utilizing advanced

technologies, it is possible to achieve substantial reduction in radiation exposure while maintaining diagnostic quality.

Another important consideration is the role of education and awareness in improving radiation safety. Continued training radiologists, technologists and referring clinicians is essential to ensure appropriate use of CT imaging and implementation of dose optimization strategies. Emphasis on justification and optimization principles can further contribute to reducing unnecessary radiation exposure in pediatric patients.

While this review provides a comprehensive overview of current trends, certain limitations should be acknowledged. The heterogeneity of the included studies, including differences in design, patient populations, and reporting methods, limits direct comparability. Additionally, the reliance on aggregated data restricts detailed analysis of individual patient-level factors. Despite these limitations, the findings offer valuable insights into existing practices and highlight areas for improvement.

Further efforts should focus on developing standardized guidelines for pediatric CT imaging, including clear definition of protocol categories and consistent reporting of radiation dose parameters. Greater collaboration across institutions and the establishment of centralized dose registries may facilitate benchmarking and promote best practices. Continued evaluation of emerging technologies and dose reduction techniques will also be essential in advancing radiation safety.

In conclusion, radiation dose in pediatric NCCT head imaging remains highly variable, influenced by a combination of technical, procedural and institutional factors. Although recent trends suggest improvement, there is a continued need for standardized protocol, consistent dose monitoring, and ongoing optimization. Strengthening these practices is essential to ensuring safe and effective imaging in pediatric populations and to minimizing unnecessary radiation exposure while preserving diagnostic value.

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